

Polarographic Study of the Biuret Reactions of Succinimide

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The biuret reaction of succinimide has been studied polarographically in the aqueous and aqueous ethanolic media. In the aqueous medium the complex is reduced in two reversible steps, each involving a transfer of one electron, whereas in the latter medium distortion of both the waves occurs. Plots of log. conc. succinimide vs. $E_{1/2}$ values of the two waves provide straight lines with slopes of 0.180 and 0.175 for cupric and cuprous ions, indicating possibility of the existence of hexa- and tri-co-ordinated complexes respectively.

Of the physical methods usually employed for investigating the biuret complexes, electrometric methods have attracted little attention. This is particularly true for polarography. Recently we carried out a number of investigations¹ in this direction and the conclusions arrived at led us to believe that other less-familiar biuret reactions could also be critically studied with the help of this technique. The present communication deals with the copper-succinimide reaction, investigated polarographically in the aqueous and aqueous-ethanolic media.

The biuret reaction of acid imides has not been studied fully. Schiff² in his generalisation of the groups responsible for the biuret reaction did not include these compounds. Tschugaeff³ reported the reaction in the ammoniacal, aqueous ethanolic, and pyridine media. Ley and Werner⁴ worked out the hydrolytic nature of the copper-succinimide complex and Rising and Johnson⁵ investigated the composition of the complex obtained by the interaction of succinimide and copper sulphate in presence of an ethanolic solution of barium hydroxide. But for these references, nothing worth mentioning exists in the literature and much remains to be done to elucidate the nature of the biuret reaction in the case of acid imides.

EXPERIMENTAL

Succinimide (m.p. 124°) was prepared according to the method of Clark and Behr⁶. A 2.0M solution of the reagent (for preliminary work) was obtained by dissolving the requisite amount in double distilled water. Another solution (1.0 M) was prepared in equivalent concentration of KOH.

Copper sulphate (A.R.) and cuprous chloride⁷ (obtained by reducing cupric chloride with pure metallic copper) were dissolved in double distilled water and 1.0M KCl respec-

1. Malik *et al.*, *J. Polarograp. Soc.*, 1959, 2; *Naturewiss.*, 1959, 46, 378; 1961, 48, 47; *Curr. Sci.*, 1959, 28, 364.
2. *Annalen*, 1898, 299, 236; *Ber.*, 1899, 29, 298.
3. *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2899.
4. *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 4040.
5. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 89, 709.
6. "Org. Syn.", Coll. Vol. II, p. 562.
7. Fernelius, "Inorganic Synthesis", Vol. II, McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, 1946, p. 1.

tively to prepare the solutions. Potassium chloride (A.R.) and gelatin (extra pure) solutions were used as the supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor, respectively.

Fisher Electrode with Multiflex galvanometer (MGF2) in the external circuit was used for the manual recording of the polarograms. The cell consisted of a saturated calomel electrode as the reference and the dropping mercury electrode as the cathode. Inert atmosphere was maintained by passing a current of purified nitrogen. The temperature was maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ on keeping the cell immersed in a thermostatic water bath (Townson and Mercer).

Preliminary experiments showed that the complex was not stable under ordinary conditions and in almost all cases (containing varying proportion of the two reagents) precipitation of copper hydroxide took place on adding an excess of KOH. Optimum condition for obtaining a sample for polarographic studies was determined. Most satisfactory results were achieved by using the solution of the imide, prepared in equivalent concentration of the KOH solution, for obtaining the complex. For determining the composition of the complex, polarograms were taken in varying concentrations of succinimide (Fig. 1). Attempt was also made to study the complex in the aqueous ethanolic medium, but the waves were not well defined and the distortion was proportional to the ethanolic concentration. Polarograms with varying concentrations of copper sulphate and KOH were also taken, but these were of little value from quantitative stand point.

FIG. 1 Polarograms of the soln.

The soln. consists of 0.04M-Cu SO₄ (0.5 ml), 2M-KCl (2 ml), 0.02% gelatin (1 ml), and 1M succinimide: (1) 16.5, (2) 14.5, (3) 12.5, (4) 10.5, (5) 8.5, (6) 6.5, (7) 4.5 ml. Total volume=20 ml.

DISCUSSION

Succinimide forms a violet complex in alkaline medium in presence of ethanol, but as the concentration of the latter is decreased, the colour changes from violet to bluish violet. Under the aqueous conditions the complex hydrolyses very easily and a precipitate of copper hydroxide settles down if a very large excess of succinimide is not present. In presence of a large excess of succinimide, the complex (bluish violet in colour) is reduced at the d.m.e., providing two waves. Both the waves were found to be reversible (Tome's method³) and one electron was involved in the reduction of each step (Fig. 1)

According to Kolthoff and Lingane⁹, such a stepwise reduction in a complex can be represented by the following equations:

$$\text{I. } E_{\frac{1}{2}^{\text{I}}} = E^{\circ}_1 - 0.059 \log \frac{K_{\text{ox}}}{K_{\text{red}}} - (p-q) 0.059 \log C_x$$

$$\text{II. } E_{\frac{1}{2}^{\text{II}}} = E^{\circ}_2 - 0.059 \log \frac{K_{\text{red}}}{K_a} - q 0.059 \log C_x$$

where p and q are the number of molecules combined with Cu^{2+} and Cu^+ respectively, $E_{\frac{1}{2}^{\text{I}}}$ and $E_{\frac{1}{2}^{\text{II}}}$ are the half-wave potentials for the first and the second waves; K_{ox} , K_{red} and K_a are proportional to the square root of the diffusion coefficient of the oxidised, reduced, and an amalgam respectively; C_x is the concentration of the complexing agent and E°_1 and E°_2 are the standard potentials of the following two reactions:

On plotting $E_{\frac{1}{2}^{\text{I}}}$ and $E_{\frac{1}{2}^{\text{II}}}$ against $-\log$ conc. of succinimide, two straight lines (Fig. 2, curves I and II), each having a slope of 0.180 and 0.175, respectively, were obtained. From these slopes the values of the number of molecules combined with one cupric and one cuprous ions came out to be 6 and 3 respectively. The corresponding formulas may then be represented as:

These co-ordination numbers, viz., 6 for the cupric and 3 for the cuprous ions, although unusual, are sometimes met with in the azido and halo-complexes.

On comparing the above results with those of other birust reactions studied previously¹, it will be seen that in the previous cases the complex was reduced directly to the metallic state (providing one polarographic wave), whereas in the present studies, two waves are obtained, indicating existence of both $\text{Cu}(\text{I})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complexes. Such a behaviour is not uncommon if cuprous ions are assumed to form complex with succinimide.

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